

TENSILE CHARACTERISTICS OF JUTE ROPE PLAIN FABRIC REINFORCED POLYLACTIC ACID COMPOSITES

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Keywords: Rope, Jute Fiber, Braiding, PLA, Tension

ABSTRACT

Manufacturing and tensile properties of jute rope plain fabric reinforced Poly(lactic acid) (PLA) composites were investigated in the current research. A rope braiding machine was used to braid jute yarns to get jute ropes. The ropes were used as weft and warp yarns, which supplied to a weaving loom, to weave reinforced fabrics. The fabrics are plain woven construction. In this study, the jute fiber ropes were treated in sodium hydroxide to purify the reinforced fabrics. The mechanical properties of jute ropes before and after sodium hydroxide treatment were studied in the paper. The treated factors, concentration of sodium hydroxide solution and time for heating as composite manufacturing, are discussed in detail. A hot-press machine was used to make the jute rope plain fabric/PLA composites. The tensile, characteristics of the ropes and composites are evaluated by a material test system (MTS810). The failure phenomenon of the composites was, also, discussed, in the current experiment. Experimental results show that the jute rope plain fabric/PLA composites have good tensile strength, modulus, and energy absorption.

1 INTRODUCTION

Natural fibers, such as jute and cotton, are less reinforcement effect due to their low strength. The congenital defects limit the application of natural fiber composites. If we want to broad the application of natural fiber composites, we must enhance the properties of natural fibers. Figure 1 shows an effective method to strong natural fibers. This motivation drives from the rope for tug-of-war. The tug-of-war rope is made by braiding 8 to 12 intermediate ropes. And the intermediate ropes are also made by braiding 8 to 12 natural fiber yarns. Finally, the natural fiber ropes become stronger by a series of braiding. So, in the current study, we used the braid method to enhance jute fiber yarns and then the braided jute fiber ropes are used as weft and warp yarns to weave reinforced fabrics.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 MATERIALS

Figure 2 shows the experimental procedures. The jute fiber yarns are 8-10 Ne in count, 0.3 mm in diameter and 3.28 g in tenacity. Commercial PLA resin was used as matrix material. Sodium hydroxide solution with various contents (5%, 10%, and 15%) was used to modify the braided jute

ropes.

2.2 BRAIDING AND WEAVING

A rope braiding machine with 12 carriers was used to make the jute ropes. The braided rope is 3.16 mm in diameter and 135.3 Ne in count. The jute lopes are used as warp and weft yarns to weave reinforced fabrics by a Dobby loom. The loom has 16 heddle frames. The pattern of the jute fabric is plain weaving. There are 5.1 ends per inch and 3.04 picks per inch in warp and weft, respectively. The average thickness of jute fabric is 6.3 mm.

2.3 NAOH TREATMENT

The braided ropes are treated with sodium hydroxide solution. The weight contents of the solution are 5%, 10%, and 15%. The ropes were dipped in the mentioned solution for 30 min., 60 min., or 120 min. After the dipped process, the ropes are water cleaning. The cleaned ropes should be dried and kept in an oven prior to weaving procedure.

2.4. COMPOSITES PREPARATION AND TESTING

The jute rope plain fabric reinforced PLA composites had been made on a hot press machine. Three heating temperature (180°C, 190°C, and 200°C) and two heating time (25 min and 45 min) were chosen to optimize processing parameters. So there are six processes in this experiment. Every process includes preheating stage under the chosen temperature for 10 minutes and pressing stage for the remaining time. The product composites are A4 size and the thickness of composite controlled at six mm. Finally, the composites were cut into specimens according to the referred ASTM standard. Tensile testing was carried out on the composite samples and ropes samples by MTS 810 machine. The tensile strength, modulus, breaking strain, and energy to break are discussed in the current study.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 ROPE TENSION

Figure 3 and Figure 4 show that increasing the sodium hydroxide concentration increased the shrinkage and weight loss of jute ropes, respectively. Figure 5 indicates that increasing treatment time increased the jute rope shrinkage. High sodium hydroxide concentrations and treatment time (Figure 6) damage the structure of jute fiber and the compactness of braiding architecture of jute ropes. It also affects the capability to resist tensile load. Therefore, the strength of jute rope reduced with increasing the sodium hydroxide concentration. For high NaOH concentration (15%), the strength reduce rate up to about 40%. 15% NaOH concentration exhibited the mass damage of jute ropes. For low NaOH concentration, it can keep the strength and less damage jute ropes. However, it could not remove oil and wax with that the jute fiber possessed. Without removing oil and wax reduced the wetting compatibility between jute fiber and PLA resin. So, the appropriate concentration and time for the jute ropes treated with sodium hydroxide solution is 10% and 30 min.

During the weaving prepare process, the entire weft and warp yarns (jute ropes) should be treated with sodium hydroxide solution under the suggested concentration and treatment time. The details of tensile properties (shrinkage, weight loss, maximum load, maximum displacement and strength reduce rate) are summarized in Table 1.

3.2 COMPOSITE TENSION

As the mentioned composites preparation, the hot pressing temperatures are set at 180°C, 190°C, or 200°C. According to observations of the melting flow of PLA and the etiolating of jute fibers, the appropriate hot press parameters were set at 190°C. For low temperature and less hot pressing time, PLA resin has high viscosity and low fluidity. These cause to hardly wetting between PLA resin and jute fibers. Low fluidity also distorts jute fabric while hot pressing process. In addition, the jute fibers become brittle and discolor at high temperature. So the following tensile specimens were prepared at

190°C for 25min or 45 min.

Figure 7 and Figure 8 show that the effect of hot-press heating time on the maximum tensile modulus of jute fabric/PLA composites with and without 10% NaOH treatment while tension in warp and weft direction, respectively. The jute rope/PLA composites have good tensile modulus when the ropes treated with 10% NaOH solution. And the more heating time while composites manufacturing process the jute rope/PLA composites possess higher tensile modulus both in warp and weft directional tension. Although high hot-press heating time was good in tensile modulus, it causes weak in tensile strength (Figure 9 and Figure 10). Tensile strength, modulus, breaking strain, and energy to break of jute rope fabric reinforced PLA composites are listed in Table 2. The jute rope/PLA composites that the jute ropes treated with NaOH solution have low breaking strain and less breaking energy absorption. Finally, all specimens failed in brittle.

Figure 3. Effect of NaOH concentration on the rope shrinkage after 30 minutes treatment.

Figure 4. Effect of treatment time on the weight loss of jute rope with various NaOH concentrations.

Figure 5. Effect of treatment time on the rope shrinkage under 10% NaOH concentration

Figure 6. Effect of treatment time on the maximum tensile loads of jute rope with various NaOH concentrations.

Figure 7. Effect of composite hot-press heating time on the maximum tensile modulus of jute fabric/PLA composites with and without 10% NaOH treatment while tension in warp direction.

Figure 8. Effect of hot-press heating time on the maximum tensile modulus of jute fabric/PLA composites with and without 10% NaOH treatment while tension in weft direction.

Figure 9. Effect of hot-press heating time on the tensile strength of jute fabric/PLA composites with and without 10% NaOH treatment while tension in warp direction.

Figure 10. Effect of hot-press heating time on the tensile strength of jute fabric/PLA composites with and without 10% NaOH treatment while tension in warp direction.

Table 1. Effect of Treating Parameters on the Shrinkage, Weight Loss, and Tensile Properties of Jute Ropes.

Rope Name	R0	R0530	R0560	R05120	R1030	R1060	R10120	R1530	R1560	R15120
NaOH Concentration	No	5%			10%			15%		
Time (min.)	No	30	60	120	30	60	120	30	60	120
Shrinkage (%)	0	12.15	13.59	14.98	17.84	19.03	19.85	24.04	25.66	27.88
Weight Loss (%)	OW: 1.52g	4.95%	5.88%	6.52%	7.38%	8.12%	8.34%	9.34%	10.77%	12.07%
Max. Load (kgf)	39.47	36.85	35.44	33.19	29.45	26.38	24.20	23.60	21.47	20.01
Max. Displacement (mm)	23.81	22.72	24.725	26.98	31.28	32.05	33.54	34.4	35.48	36.38
Strength Reduce Rate (%)	--	6.64%	10.21%	15.91%	25.39%	33.16%	38.69%	40.21%	40.54%	41.70%

R0: Ropes without NaOH Treatment.

OW: The average weight of ropes without NaOH Treatment.

R0530: It indicates that the ropes treated with 5% NaOH solution for 30 min.

R0560 indicates treated with 5% NaOH solution for 60 min. ...and so on.

Table 2. Tensile Properties of Jute Fabric/PLA Composites.

Loading Direction	Warp				Weft			
	No		Yes		No		Yes	
Composite Manufacturing Time (min.)	25	45	25	45	25	45	25	45
Modulus (MPa)	3482.18	3646.02	3588.65	3714.76	3603.64	3795.91	3750.87	4096.19
Break Stress (MPa)	40.01	28.11	43.32	36.28	34.57	24.67	36.97	27.75
Strain at Break (%)	1.59	1.18	2.3	1.67	1.56	1.14	1.98	1.07
Energy to Break (N*mm)	7652.52	6364.42	13435.14	8317.17	5466.27	4745.76	8241.32	6862.86
Failure Image								

4 CONCLUSIONS

Braiding skill makes jute fiber stronger and broadens the application of jute composites. The jute ropes which treat with 10% sodium hydroxide solution have good wetting compatibility with PLA resin.

Good jute plain fabrics with jute ropes as warp and weft yarns could be woven by pre-treating the jute ropes with a starch solution and controlling the tension while weaving. Enhanced jute rope plain fabric reinforced PLA composites were developed by a hot-press method at 190°C for 25 min. The jute rope plain fabric reinforced PLA composites have well in tensile strength.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work was supported by the National Science Council of Taiwan, R. O. C. through the research grant NSC100-2622-E-238-001-CC3. The authors with to thank all partners involved for the contributions: Chin-chih Yang and Zi-Jie Lin.

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